

Replication Report, Brookhart et al. (2006)

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² not applicable

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Abstract

This report describes the replication of “Variable Selection for Propensity Score Models” by Brookhart et al. (Brookhart et al. 2006). The original article provided clear descriptions of the simulation methods, which made it relatively easy to replicate the simulations. In particular when formulas were provided it was straightforward to implement the intended approach. Furthermore, the data-generating mechanism was depicted in a figure, which was helpful in understanding the simulation set up. The main difficulty of the replication was that some of the results were presented as figures, which made it more difficult to compare that results were replicated (i) because it is more difficult to compare than numbers in a table and (ii) because the approach to creating the figure was not fully described (as it is irrelevant to the paper itself). Specific software implementations were not described clearly, but this did not hamper replicability of results. For example, no packages in R were referenced for estimation of the splines or c-statistic (which makes sense given the year of publication). Results of the replication are presented below.

1 Introduction

This replication report documents the replication attempt of the simulation study “Variable Selection for Propensity Score Models” by Brookhart et al. (Brookhart et al. 2006). Following the definition of Rougier et al. (2017) we understand the replication of a published study as writing and running new code based on the description provided in the original publication with the aim of obtaining the same results.

The study was replicated independently by another duo. We will briefly discuss overlapping findings and differences at the end of the discussion section.

2 Method

2.1 Information basis

The replication was performed based on information reported in the original manuscript.

2.2 Data Generating Mechanism

Information provided in the above mentioned sources indicated that the following simulation factors were systematically varied in generating the artificial data.

2.2.1 Experiment 1

Simulation factor	No. levels	Levels
<i>Varied</i>		
Number of observations	2	500; 2500
<i>Fixed</i>		
Standard deviation of covariates	1	1
The intercept of the model for the conditional mean of outcome Y on a log-scale	1	0.5
The conditional association between covariate X1 and outcome Y on a log-scale	1	4
The conditional association between covariate X2 and outcome Y on a log-scale	1	1

Simulation factor	No. levels	Levels
The conditional association between covariate X3 and outcome Y on a log-scale	1	0
The conditional association between exposure A and outcome Y on a log-scale	1	0.5
The intercept of the model for the conditional mean of exposure A on a log-scale	1	0
The conditional association between covariate X1 and exposure A on a log-scale	1	0.5
The conditional association between covariate X2 and exposure A on a log-scale	1	0
The conditional association between covariate X3 and exposure A on a log-scale	1	0.75

2.2.2 Experiment 1, sensitivity

Simulation factor	No. levels	Levels
<i>Varied</i>		
Number of observations	2	500; 2500
Standard deviation of covariates, per covariate (X1, X2, X3)	2	0.5; 1.5
The conditional association between exposure A and outcome Y on a log-scale	2	0.25; 1
<i>Fixed</i>		
The intercept of the model for the conditional mean of outcome Y on a log-scale	1	0.5

Simulation factor	No. levels	Levels
The conditional association between covariate X1 and outcome Y on a log-scale	1	4
The conditional association between covariate X2 and outcome Y on a log-scale	1	1
The conditional association between covariate X3 and outcome Y on a log-scale	1	0
The intercept of the model for the conditional mean of exposure A on a log-scale	1	-1
The conditional association between covariate X1 and exposure A on a log-scale	1	0.5
The conditional association between covariate X2 and exposure A on a log-scale	1	0
The conditional association between covariate X3 and exposure A on a log-scale	1	0.75

2.2.3 Experiment 2

Simulation factor	No. levels	Levels
<i>Varied</i>		
Number of observations	2	500; 2500
The conditional association between covariate X1 and outcome Y on a log-scale	21	0; 0.01; 0.02; ...; 0.2
The conditional association between covariate X1 and exposure A on a log-scale	26	0; 0.05; 0.10; ...; 1.25
<i>Fixed</i>		
Standard deviation of covariate X1	1	1

Simulation factor	No. levels	Levels
The intercept of the model for the conditional mean of outcome Y on a log-scale (not defined in main text)	1	0.5
The conditional association between exposure A and outcome Y on a log-scale	1	0.5
The intercept of the model for the conditional mean of exposure A on a log-scale (not defined in main text)	1	0

The design was full-factorial in the main analyses of Experiment 1 and Experiment 2. For the sensitivity analyses of Experiment 1, all parameters were held at their default values while a single parameter was altered.

2.3 Comparison

The study compares the exposure effect estimated under various (mis)specifications of the propensity score model, where covariate X1 (a confounder), X2 (a predictor of the outcome) or X3 (an instrumental variable) or a combination of these covariates were included in the propensity scores to illustrate variable selection problems in propensity score modelling. The exposure effect was estimated using two methods; (i) the propensity scores were entered into the outcome model as a parametric spline and (ii) using subclassification in which strata are defined by quintiles of the estimated propensity scores and taking the average treatment effect across strata.

2.4 Performance measures

The variance, bias and mean squared error (MSE) of the log-linear relation between the exposure and the outcome were evaluated.

2.5 Technical implementation

While the original simulation study was carried out in the R programming environment version 1.9.1 running on a Windows platform, our replication was implemented using R version 3.6.3 on a Windows platform (details regarding software versions can be obtained from the section Reproducibility Information). The corresponding R code can be obtained from https://github.com/replisims/Brookhart_MA-2006/.

The following table provides an overview of replicator degrees of freedom, i.e. decisions that had to be made by the replicators because of insufficient or contradicting information. Issues were resolved by discussion

among the replicators. Decisions were based on what the replicators perceived to be the most likely implementation with likeliness estimated by common practice and/or guideline recommendations. Wherever feasible multiple interpretations were implemented.

Issue	Replicator decision	Justification
<p>It was unclear how the x-axes of Figure 3 and Figure 4 were derived. The results section of the manuscript stated “Because the parameter beta_1 in the probit model is not directly interpretable, we transform it into a “relative risk” (relative exposure prevalence). This is done by computing the probability of treatment at the 75th percentile of X_1 and dividing it by the probability of treatment at the 25th percentile of X_1—in other words, the probability of treatment for someone with a moderately large value of X_1 divided by the probability of treatment for someone with a moderately small value of X_1.” and “The increase in variance did not depend on the strength of association between X1 and Y (data not presented)”.</p> <p>---</p>	<p>We derived the values for the x-axis as $\frac{\text{pnorm}(\beta_1 x_{.75}) - \text{pnorm}(\beta_1 x_{.25})}{\text{pnorm}(\alpha_1 x_{.75}) - \text{pnorm}(\alpha_1 x_{.25})}$. For Figure 2, we took the variance over all scenarios with the same beta1 value, but possibly with different alpha1 values.</p> <p>---</p>	<p>---</p>

Issue	Replicator decision	Justification
<p>The manuscript stated “the exposure effects were estimated by adjusting for the PS in a multivariable Poisson model of the outcome in which the effect of the estimated PS was flexibly modeled through a cubic regression spline with three interior knot points placed at quartiles of the estimated PS.” We were unsure how the cubic spline estimation was implemented.</p> <p>---</p>	<p>This decision was non-fixed due to lack of subject-matter knowledge. We used the function bs() in splines package, with specifying three knots splines::bs(PS, knots = quantile(PS, probs = c(0.25, 0.5, 0.75)))</p> <p>---</p>	<p>Default implementation (Perperoglou et al. 2019)</p> <p>---</p>
<p>For experiment 2, the methods section mentioned that adjustment for the propensity score was only through the spline function, yet the results section fitted the quintile approach as well.</p> <p>---</p>	<p>---</p>	<p>Results were not similar to the original manuscript.</p> <p>---</p>
<p>For experiment 2, the intercept values for the generation of A and Y are not mentioned explicitly</p> <p>---</p>	<p>We used the values used in experiment 1</p> <p>---</p>	<p>The paragraph explaining the data-generating mechanism starts with “Both simulation experiments employed the same basic data-generating process”</p> <p>---</p>
<p>The manuscript stated: “All simulations were performed in R, version 1.9.1 (16, 17), running on a Windows XP platform, using software created by one of the authors (M. A. B.)” Equivocal which additional software was used.</p> <p>---</p>	<p>We assumed the authors referred to R scripts.</p> <p>---</p>	<p>---</p>

Issue	Replicator decision	Justification
Not reported how C-statistic was estimated (but this is relatively unambiguous)	Hmisc::somers2(PS, data[,"exposure"])[,"C"]	Used widely applied Hmisc package.

2.6 Replicating figures

Replication of a figure posed a small challenge. It is slightly more difficult to judge whether a figure is replicated as compared to whether a table is replicated (although the degree of variability between the replication and original might have been similar in our case, since we did not have access to seeds to replicate the original tables).

Additionally, we used information from the original article only (no source code) and it is not likely that the procedure for creating the figure is described in the manuscript (which would detract from the main message and waste words). Hence, the most researchers degrees of freedom were spend on creating Figure 2-4. We originally created a figure for fixed values of alpha1 or beta1, instead of averaging over all possible other values, which showed larger variability than the original figure. Also, before we found the description in the results section, we used exponentiated values of the log-linear associations to obtain the relative risks.

3 Results

3.1 Simulation descriptives

3.2 Replication of result tables

	Variable(s) in propensity score model							
	X1	X2	X3	X1+X2	X1+X3	X2+X3	X1+X2+X3	None
n = 500								
Bias x 10	0.07	5.94	7.35	0.08	-0.00	7.37	0.03	5.99
Variance x 10	0.30	0.24	0.49	0.21	0.44	0.40	0.33	0.40
MSE x 10	0.30	3.78	5.88	0.22	0.44	5.82	0.33	3.98
Average c-statistic	0.67	0.52	0.76	0.67	0.82	0.76	0.82	
n = 2,500								
Bias x 100	-0.02	59.25	73.42	-0.10	-0.01	73.37	-0.07	59.17
Variance x 100	0.68	0.59	1.05	0.51	0.90	0.87	0.72	0.90
MSE x 100	0.68	35.70	54.95	0.51	0.90	54.71	0.72	35.91
Average cstatistic	0.67	0.51	0.76	0.67	0.81	0.76	0.81	

Table 5: Table 1 from original manuscript. None of the values are notably different from the original manuscript (not notably different meaning differences are likely explained by random variability for instance due to different seeds).

	Variable(s) in propensity score model							
	X1	X2	X3	X1+X2	X1+X3	X2+X3	X1+X2+X3	None
n = 500								
Bias x 10	0.35	6.07	7.94	0.41	0.33	7.98	0.33	5.99
Variance x 10	0.22	0.16	0.49	0.17	0.52	0.41	0.53	0.40
MSE x 10	0.23	3.84	6.79	0.19	0.53	6.79	0.54	3.98
n = 2,500								
Bias x 100	2.94	59.49	76.03	2.96	6.23	76.03	6.34	59.17
Variance x 100	0.45	0.31	1.11	0.28	1.13	0.92	0.99	0.90
MSE x 100	0.54	35.70	58.92	0.37	1.52	58.72	1.40	35.91

Table 6: Table 2 from original manuscript. None of the values are notably different from the original manuscript (not notably different meaning differences are likely explained by random variability for instance due to different seeds).

	Variable(s) in propensity score model							
	X1	X2	X3	X1+X2	X1+X3	X2+X3	X1+X2+X3	None
Original								
Bias x 10	0.07	5.94	7.35	0.08	0	7.37	0.03	5.99
Variance x 10	0.3	0.24	0.49	0.21	0.44	0.4	0.33	0.4
MSE x 10	0.3	3.78	5.88	0.22	0.44	5.82	0.33	3.98
Decrease in the variance of X1								
Bias x 10	-0.05	2.81	3.59	0.01	-0.02	3.64	0.02	2.78
Variance x 10	0.29	0.2	0.48	0.19	0.38	0.37	0.27	0.37
MSE x 10	0.29	0.98	1.77	0.19	0.38	1.69	0.27	1.15
Increase in the variance of X1								
Bias x 10	0.09	8.46	10.09	0.11	0.1	10.1	0.11	8.47
Variance x 10	0.32	0.27	0.48	0.24	0.46	0.4	0.36	0.41
MSE x 10	0.33	7.43	10.65	0.24	0.46	10.6	0.36	7.59
Decrease in the variance of X2								
Bias x 10	0.02	5.99	7.42	0.02	0.02	7.43	0.04	5.99
Variance x 10	0.07	0.15	0.2	0.05	0.12	0.18	0.09	0.17
MSE x 10	0.07	3.73	5.71	0.05	0.12	5.7	0.09	3.76
Increase in the variance of X2								
Bias x 10	-0.05	5.88	7.33	-0.04	-0.02	7.32	-0.05	5.86
Variance x 10	1.28	0.53	1.7	1.06	1.68	1.44	1.4	1.37
MSE x 10	1.28	3.99	7.07	1.06	1.68	6.8	1.4	4.8
Decrease in the variance of X3								
Bias x 10	0.02	6.94	7.37	0	0.04	7.37	0.03	6.91
Variance x 10	0.36	0.25	0.43	0.24	0.42	0.36	0.32	0.41
MSE x 10	0.36	5.06	5.86	0.23	0.42	5.78	0.32	5.18
Increase in the variance of X3								
Bias x 10	0.05	5.11	7.43	0.07	-0.03	7.44	-0.04	5.07
Variance x 10	0.3	0.27	0.57	0.23	0.51	0.49	0.4	0.41
MSE x 10	0.3	2.89	6.09	0.23	0.51	6.02	0.4	2.99
Decrease in alpha4								
Bias x 10	0.07	5.95	7.41	0.03	0.02	7.39	0	6
Variance x 10	0.33	0.23	0.47	0.23	0.46	0.36	0.33	0.4
MSE x 10	0.33	3.77	5.96	0.23	0.46	5.82	0.33	3.99

	Variable(s) in propensity score model							None
	X1	X2	X3	X1+X2	X1+X3	X2+X3	X1+X2+X3	
Increase in alpha4								
Bias x 10	0.08	5.92	7.33	0.02	0.04	7.3	0	5.97
Variance x 10	0.3	0.25	0.49	0.21	0.44	0.4	0.33	0.4
MSE x 10	0.3	3.76	5.86	0.21	0.44	5.73	0.33	3.97
Decrease in beta0								
Bias x 10	0.03	5.8	7.03	-0.01	-0.04	7.02	-0.07	5.75
Variance x 10	0.32	0.22	0.53	0.21	0.47	0.38	0.3	0.41
MSE x 10	0.32	3.58	5.47	0.21	0.47	5.31	0.3	3.72

Table 7: Table 3 from original manuscript. None of the values are notably different from the original manuscript (not notably different meaning differences are likely explained by random variability for instance due to different seeds).

3.3 Replication of result figures

Figure 1: Replication of Figure 2 in original manuscript. Results are very similar.

Figure 2: Replication of Figure 3 in original manuscript. Results are very similar.

Figure 3: Replication of Figure 4 in original manuscript. The left panel is different from the original manuscript.

4 Discussion

4.1 Replicability

The manuscript by Brookhart and colleagues (Brookhart et al. 2006) provided a clear description of the simulation approach, which ensured that replication of the results was nearly fully possible and relatively straightforward. The authors (likely) implemented default procedures and provided formulas and a figure to depict the data-generating mechanism, thereby capturing all relevant information.

4.2 Replicator degrees of freedom

The main guesses that we had to make were about specific implementations of the procedures. For example, for estimation of the cubic splines or construction of the x-axis of figures. These decisions likely have not had a large impact on the results. Making analysis code available (as is more common nowadays than back in 2006) would likely have resolved all issues.

Reflecting on the replication process, we found the asymmetrical behaviour of our checks interesting. When we found a result similar to the maintext, we would continue programming the next part of the analysis. However, when we ran into a discrepancy, we tried different implementations (like explained in section 2.6) to obtain the original result.

4.3 Equivalence of results

By and large, the replicated results are equivalent to the original results. The orders of magnitude and directions are similar and we would draw the same conclusions based on the results. Figure 4 is the only aspect we could not fully replicate.

4.4 Comparison with independent replication team

The duo that performed an independent replication of the study was successful in replicating the study as well. A discussion of the replication process provided the following observations about reporting of simulation studies.

First, describing procedures exactly in the order they are performed facilitates replication. In particular, Brookhart and colleagues presented some methods (for generation of figures) in their results, and hence we sometimes had to go back and forth through the text while writing the replication code.

Additionally, it is quite challenging for authors to address an audience with different expertises and skills (which is arguably quite diverse for simulations studies). For example, Brookhart and colleagues did not explicitly mention that propensity scores were estimated from a propensity score model. Different notation could have clarified this, but it is not always desirable to introduce mathematical notation, depending on the readership of a journal.

Overall, it's been a helpful experience to replicate a simulation study solely from the main text in an article that provided insight into the choices regarding and consequences of the way methods and results are presented.

5 Contributions

Authors made the following contributions according to the CRediT framework <https://casrai.org/credit/>

Primary Replicator:

- Data Curation
- Formal Analysis (lead)
- Investigation
- Software
- Visualization (lead)
- Writing - Original Draft Preparation
- Writing - Review & Editing

Co-Pilot:

- Formal Analysis (supporting)
- Investigation
- Software (supporting)
- Visualization (supporting)
- Validation
- Writing - Review & Editing

References

- Brookhart, M Alan, Sebastian Schneeweiss, Kenneth J Rothman, Robert J Glynn, Jerry Avorn, and Til Stürmer. 2006. "Variable Selection for Propensity Score Models." *American Journal of Epidemiology* 163 (12): 1149–56.
- Perperoglou, Aris, Willi Sauerbrei, Michal Abrahamowicz, and Matthias Schmid. 2019. "A Review of Spline Function Procedures in R." *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 19 (1): 46.
- Rougier, Nicolas P, Konrad Hinsén, Frédéric Alexandre, Thomas Arildsen, Lorena A Barba, Fabien CY Benureau, C Titus Brown, et al. 2017. "Sustainable Computational Science: The Rescience Initiative." *PeerJ Computer Science* 3: e142.

Appendix

Additional result

<insert additional results not reported in the original article or results presented in an alternative way>

5.1 Code organization

The code and the files associated are organized in the form of a research compendium which can be found in the following git repository https://github.com/replisims/Brookhart_MA-2006/

```
## .
## +-- defs.aux
## +-- defs.tex
## +-- flowchart.PNG
## +-- Lato-Black.ttf
## +-- Lato-BlackItalic.ttf
## +-- Lato-Bold.ttf
## +-- Lato-BoldItalic.ttf
## +-- Lato-Italic.ttf
## +-- Lato-Regular.ttf
## +-- paper.log
## +-- paper.pdf
## +-- paper.Rmd
## +-- paper.tex
## +-- references.bib
## +-- UbuntuMono-Bold.ttf
## +-- UbuntuMono-BoldItalic.ttf
## +-- UbuntuMono-Italic.ttf
## \-- UbuntuMono-Regular.ttf
```

- foldername: contains <insert description>
- filename: contains <insert description>
- ...

Reproducibility Information

This report was last updated on 2020-11-11 20:54:10. The simulation replication was conducted using the following computational environment and dependencies:

```
## - Session info -----
## setting value
## version R version 3.6.3 (2020-02-29)
## os Windows 10 x64
## system x86_64, mingw32
## ui RTerm
## language (EN)
## collate Dutch_Netherlands.1252
```

```

## ctype    Dutch_Netherlands.1252
## tz       Europe/Berlin
## date     2020-11-11
##
## - Packages -----
## package      * version   date      lib
## assertthat   0.2.1     2019-03-21 [1]
## backports    1.2.0     2020-11-02 [1]
## callr        3.4.3     2020-03-28 [1]
## cli          2.1.0     2020-10-12 [1]
## crayon       1.3.4     2017-09-16 [1]
## desc         1.2.0     2018-05-01 [1]
## devtools     2.3.1     2020-07-21 [1]
## digest       0.6.27    2020-10-24 [1]
## dplyr        * 1.0.2     2020-08-18 [1]
## ellipsis     0.3.1     2020-05-15 [1]
## evaluate     0.14      2019-05-28 [1]
## fansi        0.4.1     2020-01-08 [1]
## fs           1.4.2     2020-06-30 [1]
## generics     0.1.0     2020-10-31 [1]
## glue         1.4.2     2020-08-27 [1]
## htmltools    0.5.0     2020-06-16 [1]
## knitr        * 1.29      2020-06-23 [1]
## lifecycle    0.2.0     2020-03-06 [1]
## magrittr     1.5       2014-11-22 [1]
## memoise     1.1.0     2017-04-21 [1]
## pillar       1.4.6     2020-07-10 [1]
## pkgbuild     1.1.0     2020-07-13 [1]
## pkgconfig    2.0.3     2019-09-22 [1]
## pkgload      1.1.0     2020-05-29 [1]
## prettyunits  1.1.1     2020-01-24 [1]
## processx    3.4.3     2020-07-05 [1]
## ps           1.3.3     2020-05-08 [1]
## purrr        0.3.4     2020-04-17 [1]
## R6           2.5.0     2020-10-28 [1]
## remotes      2.2.0     2020-07-21 [1]
## RepliSimReport 0.0.0.9000 2020-09-28 [1]
## rlang        0.4.8     2020-10-08 [1]
## rmarkdown    2.3       2020-06-18 [1]
## rprojroot    1.3-2     2018-01-03 [1]
## sessioninfo  1.1.1     2018-11-05 [1]
## stringi      1.5.3     2020-09-09 [1]
## stringr      1.4.0     2019-02-10 [1]
## testthat     2.3.2     2020-03-02 [1]
## tibble       3.0.4     2020-10-12 [1]
## tidyselect   1.1.0     2020-05-11 [1]
## usethis      1.6.1     2020-04-29 [1]
## vctrs        0.3.4     2020-08-29 [1]
## withr        2.2.0     2020-04-20 [1]
## xfun         0.16      2020-07-24 [1]
## xtable       * 1.8-4     2019-04-21 [1]
## yaml         2.2.1     2020-02-01 [1]
## source
## CRAN (R 3.6.3)
## CRAN (R 3.6.3)

```

